

Bridging Ethnic Consciousness Through Purposeful Followership: Perspectives Of Select Dramatists

Oghenevize Moses Umukoro, Ph.D¹, Samuel Eromosele Azugbene²

¹Department of Theatre Arts
College of Education, Warri
Delta State
Mosesumukoro@Rocketmail.Com
08168011566

&

²Department of General Studies
College of Education, Warri
Delta State
Azugbenesamuel@Gmail.Com
08036761371

Abstract

*The quest for national integration is cardinal among nations with diverse ethnic, cultural and religious inclinations. The frequent ethnic clashes as well as calls for autonomy or secession in parts of Nigeria is an indication of a wide gap in the bond that cements the aggregate units that form the nation's federation. While Nigeria prides herself of "Unity in Diversity", it is evident, and glaring too, that elements in our diversity are antithetical to national integration. This paper examines the issue of integration through conscientious collectivism. It adopts a critical research approach by using Ola Rotimi's *If... Tragedy of the Ruled* and Sam Ukala's *The Placenta of Death* to probe how various dramatists in Nigeria appraise the issue of integration. The paper argues that the elite engage selfish politics as the main apparatus of disintegration and sharpens it with ethno-religious instruments. Inter alia, the paper advocates for a purposeful followership; followership devoid of "Zombie Spirit" but one that demands accountability and questions norms that are inimical to our collective consciousness.*

Keywords: *Integration, Ethnicity, Humanities, Drama, Unity, Ola Rotimi, Sam Ukala*

Introduction

The entity called Nigeria today, prior to its colonization and the eventual amalgamation of 1914 comprised of over two hundred independent ethnic nationalities with diverse cultures: diverse

beliefs, worldviews and socio-political orientation. The slogan "Unity in Diversity" in Nigeria is an indication that though we yearn for unity, the nation's aggregate units are diverse. This diversity is amplified by the fact that there was never a referendum during or after the era of colonialism

where the independent ethnic nationalities that form the Nigerian state agreed to come together as one entity. Consequently, while the forced union by the colonialists continues to hold the different units together as one nation, the units, as could be expected, continue to pay more allegiance to their roots than the central. This is why Justice Oputa puts it succinctly that “we don’t have Nigerians yet, but trabalists” (2005, p.9). Osammor, (2012, p.76) citing Embu (2012) also avers to the above when he points out that

We are still disunited. Leaders are interested in their own, not national identity. We are a blood thirsty and bloodletting society with no regards for sanctity of life. Nigeria is at war against itself. Selfish politicians doing all things on the basis of political exigency... our leaders failed to gather the authentic representatives of Nigerians to seek the kind of independent Nigeria they want.(76).

The political structure of the nation and implicitly, the imbalance it creates in the socio-economic distribution of the federation’s resources supports division along regional and ethnic lines. Consequently, as former Attorney-General of the Federation and Minister of Justice, Chief Bayo Ojo (SAN) notes, rather than forge a common front with a sense of national identity, Nigerians are

“returning more and more to primordial affiliation for identity, loyalty and security” Ojo (2013, np.). Insatiable greed, wanton corruption, ethnic loyalty, marginalization, all coalesces into frenzied yearns for the restructuring of the nation’s socio-economic and political landscape. Okpe, as far back at 2003 was prophetic in his assessment of the situation in Nigeria today when he posits that the nation is at a crossroad as it is “entangled in the intricate web and contradictions of having to define the substance, nature and character of its sovereignty (2003, p.1). Unarguably, the MOSOB and the Niger Delta agitations as well as the middle belt crises, which some perceive as tactical ethnic cleansing in the hands of Fulani race disguised as herdsmen, are all indications of the clear and present danger in the survival of the Nigerian sovereignty. The realization of this position by different political regimes in Nigeria had in the time past orchestrated forums for national dialogues towards achieving a true and sustainable integration of the country. The National Confab is a clear example of such moves. Regrettably, the confab yielded nothing as its outcome remains chained to the vault of political innuendoes. The resent yearning for the present administration to chart a way towards the restructuring of the country is a further manifestation of the fact that as far as the integration of the quasi federations of Nigeria is concerned, all is not well.

Various media have been echoing the political rots that fan the embers of disintegration of the country. Daily, the radio, run commentaries, the television through several discussion and news analysis programmes, community town halls forums etc., are all engaged in the talks towards bridging the gap between ethnic loyalty and the national cohesion. This paper takes a look at how this issue is articulated by some dramatists in their own quest for a united and more purposeful Nigeria.

The Humanities and National Integration

The Humanities, according to Ekoko (2012, p. 1) also called the Arts,

seek explanation to the phenomena of life and living as a continuum between the spiritual and physical; between visible and invisible worlds, the essence of Being or Existence... (Humanities) provide people with different cultural identities, the compass needed to meaningfully interact and mediate relationships both at national and transnational levels.

The above succinctly indicates that the Humanities are interested in the human condition; who is man? What is his place in the chain of existence? How does he live with his fellow man? What are his contributions towards fostering the wellbeing of the human race? These are some of the questions the humanities ask and seek answers. It is in this light that Umukoro (2010, p.15) opines that art,

whether drama, theatre, painting, etc are “living forces whose energies activate a re-creative process in man and his world; a recreation of his mind, feelings, cognition, intellect and his culture”. Ukala (2012, p. 23), citing the United States Rockefeller Commission on the Humanities also avers that “through the humanities we reflect on the fundamental question: what does it mean to be human?” Ukala notes further that the arts “reveal how people have tried to make moral, spiritual and intellectual sense of a world in which irrationality, despair, loneliness, and death are as conspicuous as birth, friendship, hope and reason”.

It is also in the above light that Campbel, Martins and Fabos (2009, p. 235) posit that film, an art form, often stimulate our desires and also “make the world seem clear, more manageable, and more understandable” as they help people to “sort through experiences that either affirmed or deviated from their own values”. Thus, the arts help humanity wade through the mirage of life. To actualize the above callings of the humanities, artist contemplates life, society and use the very residues that society thrusts at him to mould or recreate and reflect, like a mirror, how society is, and in like manner, how it ought not to be. Thus, the humanities – philosophy, history, literature, religion, the languages, visual arts and performing arts such as theatre Arts, music etc, direct their critical binoculars on the human condition.

Articulating the spirit of national integration through the humanities: Searchlight on Ola Rotimi's *If... Tragedy of the Ruled* and Sam Ukala's *The Placenta of Death*

Ola Rotimi's *If... Tragedy of the Ruled* is a satire on the political rot in Nigeria, and the need for all Nigerians, irrespective of ethnic cline to forge a bond in the reshaping of their destiny. The play looks at how politicians in Nigeria employ the mechanism of divide-and-rule to play brother against brother for their selfish interest. The setting as well as the entire characters in the play is symbolic. The setting is in the compound of "Landlord", the politician. The compound symbolizes the entire country, with its multiplicity of ethnic nationalities. Thus, in the compound are Hausa, Yoruba, Ibo, Ijaw, Edo, Calabar, Ekweri, etc. There is unity and laughter in the compound, but this is to be chattered by the Landlord, the politician. It is election time and the Landlord is vying for the seat of the Senate. He tries to compel all his tenants to swear to an oath with "juju" that they will vote for him, a quick reminder of the Okija Shrine saga, where politicians were made to swear to an oath of allegiance.

Seeing their resolve not to vote for him, in spite of all his ploys, Landlord decides to forcefully eject some of them with thugs and policemen. Of course, the thugs and the policemen symbolize the lackeys used by politicians to rig their way into political

offices, snatching ballot boxes, and even carrying out extra judicial killings. The policemen also symbolize the corrupt police and security agencies in the country that are culpable in the entrenchment of corruption and illegalities in the country.

For refusing to take such oath, he serves them quit notice, giving them just twenty four hours to evacuate his property. However, he tactically did not serve some of the tenants. Hamidu puts it clearly to Papa, his co-tenant that was not served the quit notice:

HAMIDU: ... first, your not being asked to quit, sir. I don't think is an oversight. The landlord wants to buy you over. That's what. He knows damned well that you are respected not only in this yard but in the entire neighbourhood. And so the trick.. appear kind to the popular figure, and you will hypnotize the populace for your own selfish end... As of today, the common man has no power. But who knows? For a change, the oppressed masses may soon be rescued from the forces of exploitation that has long gripped them-in the stranglehold of an inguinal hernia (p.21)

The divide and rule tactic is thus a potent instrument of not only inducement to willing accomplice, but it also engineers deep hatred amongst the ruled, the oppressed. In some parts of

the country, labour leaders have been so induced, on the long run, rather than protect the interest of their members, become handy accomplice to the political class. We have seen cases where labour leaders become Commissioners and Special Advisers to state Governors as compensation for their loyalty. Hamidu notes this when he tells his co-tenants that:

HAMIDU: ... the greatest obstacle we have to face in this struggle is not the power of the oppressors, not the trickery of reactionaries, no. The greatest obstacle is HATE. Why, because when the people are oppressed long enough they grow to hate and fight themselves, while secretly admiring the oppressor (p.22)

Hamidu's statement above is an indication that national integration should be holistic. It can only thrive when there is the air of justice, truth and equality and a strong united bond among the people. We cannot be preaching national integration and love for one another when we practice the opposite. In Ola Rotimi's *If... Tragedy of the Ruled*, Rotimi expresses this concern through Onyema, Kalada and Mr. Peters. Mr. Peters, the Scoutmaster always uses the small boys under him to seek for funds presumably to help others, but actually for his selfish end.

ONYEMA: Every time, a Scout's duty: Help others, help others". Yet he can't help Kalada Amaye. With only N10.00. He can't help him (p. 27)

Mr. Peters' action is reminiscent of what is going on in some quarters in Nigeria. Political and religious leaders preach unity, integration but their actions are devoid of these vital ingredients of integration. Like Mr. Peters, we see Pastors luring their members to "sow seeds", give tithes, help the "needy". Yet, they establish schools with proceeds from the "seeds" and offerings and tithes, which the children of the members of their congregations cannot afford the fees. Like the politicians who use thugs and dump them after elections, these leaders only create disunity by creating a wide gulf between them and those that "serve" them. But, in the words of Hamidu, "The greatest obstacle is HATE. Why, because when the people are oppressed long enough they grow to hate and fight themselves, while secretly admiring the oppressor". Rotimi, here, thus explains why people will still die for politicians and religious leaders who are fighting for their own pockets, while the poor yokels continue to "hate" and fight themselves for them.

Rotimi notes that equality and fairness are vital indices for national integration. Crude oil accounts for the main sustenance of the Nigerian economy. However, it comes at a price that also contributes

to national disintegration. The areas where crude oil is fetched is bedeviled by poverty, backwardness, hunger, ecological degradation, military brutality and other negative tendencies. One cannot feel the sense of belonging when one is short-changed by the collective. This is why Onyema is very bitter with Mr. Peters:

ONYEMA: “Bob-a-bob! “Bob-a-job!”. Every month end: “bob-a-job!”. The money we got today alone – I counted it. N37.58 kobo. Yet ordinary N10, Mr. Peters refused to give Kalada Amaye (p. 27)

The entire Boy scout group had collectively sourced for money by doing “Bob-a-bob” but the Scoutmaster, out of greed keeps the money for his private use. It is also in this vein that Fisherman complains of the degradation of the ecology of his area, where oil industry operates. The oil industry pollutes the waters and now, they can barely catch fish to survive talk less of paying tax. He takes his frustration on the oil industry. The illiterate fisherman cannot understand why the very water where his forebears earned their livelihood is now poisoned by strangers in the name of oil multinational and yet harassed and brutalized by the government. He has no other option than ask the young lawyer to give them guns to fight:

MAMA ROSA: (Interpreting for the Fisherman) E say make you give dem gun

BANJI: Give them what?

MAMA ROSA: Gun! Gun! ...he say tell gov'ment make dem gov'ment give dem gun to fight di oil company demo.

BANJI: ... government will arrest anybody who dares to disturb the oilmen!

MAMA ROSA: But di oil dey kill dem o

BANJI: It's the oil that gives life to the nation. (p. 32)

Thus, since oil gives life to the nation, it should kill those whose land gives the oil. This government's ideology, a neocolonial instinct is inimical to the spirit of integration as it sparks alienation, agitation and sectionalism.

Papa and Mama exude the spirit of integration. They are motivational characters, a rallying point for the entire neighbourhood. They are not bothered by the fact that they do not have children of their own, but consider everyone irrespective of their ethnic and religious orientation as their children. That Rotimi simply calls them PAPA and MAMA, rather than give them distinctive names is itself, symbolic. They are not ascribed to any ethnic nationality like the other characters in the play. They are symbols of unity, of national cohesion. These are the qualities that the Nigerian leaders need urgently for the continual peaceful co-existence of the country. PAPA and MAMA's

characterization therefore contrasts with that of the Landlord who symbolizes the political elite class, the never-die-hards, those who are prepared to commit all kinds of frauds to rig their way into the seat of power and render the common man in perpetual servitude. Landlord symbolizes the leaders who employ divide-and-rule tactics, using religion, ethnicity and money to blindfold unsuspecting yokels to unleash terror on their own people just as Landlord used thugs and the police to intimidate and brutalize Betty and Akpan in the play. We can draw allusion here, while scores of people were murdered (more are still being murdered) in the middle Belt of Nigeria, it took the President days to make formal pronouncement on the killings. The government of Benue had to make public outcry accusing the President and the security agencies of complacency in the murder, which he sees as a calculated ethnic cleansing (Punch, 2018). Retired Chief of Army Staff Lt. General T. Y. Danjuma is even more equivocal in his condemnation of the security forces in Nigeria and their complacency. He cried out that

The peace in this state is under assault. There is an attempt at ethnic cleansing in this state and, of course, in all the riverine state of Nigeria. We must resist it. We must stop it. Every one of us must rise up...“The armed forces are not neutral; they collude with the armed bandits that kill people, kill

Nigerians. They facilitate their movement. (<https://www.channelstv.com/2018/03/24/armed-forces-collude-with-those-behind-killings-says-t-y-danjuma/>)

The thugs and the police in the play therefore also stand for those who succumb to ethnic loyalty, individualism to hurt their own countrymen. In the play, Hamidu condemns such people and calls for unity to survive:

HAMIDU: ... we cannot build a nation on a foundation of individual self preservation! You hear? What sense is the survival of the individual in a nation drowning in a mire of misshapen values? We must survive; together we shall survive. We all indeed ... must; survive! Together (p. 82)

While Ola Rotimi in his *If... Tragedy of the Ruled* calls for unity and defiance to corruptive leaders, Sam Ukala in *The Placenta of Death* echoes the consequences of ethnicity, segregation and marginalization. In the play, Owodo, the king, in spite of the many wives in his harem could not produce a male to inherit his throne, until he married Ibo. Ibo is from the Dein family regarded as slaves in Owodoland. But the Deins do not see themselves as slaves but as victims of history. The land is divided by clear-cut polarity – the royal

class, the political elite, the rich, the poor and the “slaves”. This polarity, a kind of pseudo “ethnicity”, eventually leads to a great tragedy, resulting in death of so many in the land. The point of attack in the play rolls out from the very beginning where the class distinction is revealed in the meeting at the palace:

IHAMA: It is a new suggestion each time we are thinking of a new girl. You suggest this one’s daughter, the Oba says she’s too thin. You suggests the other one’s daughter, he says she’s too fat or that her father is the son of a poor man’s son. Now, let no one ask me for a new name or a new description. The Oba should go out and hunt for himself. And he had better not come back with another slave (p. 15)

IYASERE: That Ibo, I can’t understand what endears her so much to the king. Compare her for instance with Omon, whom I strongly recommend, and whom the Oba has refused to marry just because her father is poor.

But, Ibo will never sees herself as a slave but freeborn. She becomes a tyrant, treating everyone with disdain. Her father too, refuses to be a slave and cautions the king and all;

Emeni: We are not slaves, Iyasere, and you know it. Our grandfathers were captives of history... I swear, we will shake you out of the sweet indolence of owning slaves without a war. (*Bites the broken machete, drops it and flounces out*) (p. 31).

With the above confrontation, the die is cast. Ibo is the wife of the Oba, but from a wealthy family, though seen as slave; Omon, another wife of the Oba is from a poor family, segregated by the affluence. Iyasere, an (aristocrat), and Owodo (royalty); within the same community, humanity is disintegrated into ethnic and social bounds, disunited and each would go to any extreme to fight either to retain control or severe themselves from the pangs and stigma that the system shackled them.

The Nigerian situation could be viewed from the polarity above. A segment of the nation feels it is their birthright to cling to the seat of power. This segment is represented by Owodo (royalty). Other segment sees itself as the goose that lays the golden egg but raped and neglected. This segment is likened to Ibo, who gives birth to the heir to the throne, yet depressed and regarded as slave. Another segment, the aristocrats, is represented by Iyasere. This segment in Nigeria, symbolizes those, from the local government level to the Senate, who always claim to seats of power, who ensures that there is no election but selection in our

polity. As could be seen, there are Senators and Members of House of Assembly who have retained their seats since the past sixteen years of our nascent democratic dispensation: they belong to this group. To them, “their” seats at the Senate or wherever “is not vacant”. They will do anything within their reach like the Landlord in Rotimi’s *If... Tragedy of the Ruled* to retain their political largesse.

Omon and her parents are the common masses, raped by the political class. Just as Ibo, from the wealthy family still steals Omon’s gifts and in their place sends a roasted vulture to her, so too, are the common masses raped of their collective wealth in Nigeria. Politicians even steal from internally displaced persons (IDPs), from old retirees, from funds meant to fight terror and give succor to thousands of people who lose their loved ones and property. It is unarguably that it is only in Nigeria that people can come out openly to proclaim that a snake swallowed thirty-six million naira, public funds in their possession.

Thus, the ethnically polarized society, and its class structure represented in the play could be viewed from a Marxian perspective. While the elite class continues to engage in tendencies that perpetually chain the common man to servitude, the common man must find a way of surviving. Rotimi and Ukala, in their treatment of the subject of disintegration, marginalization and oppression,

awaken the Nigerian people from their political doldrums. For, as Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels aver in their famous *The Communist Manifesto*,

The history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles. Freeman and slave, patrician and plebian, lord and serf, guild-master and journeyman, in a word, oppressor and oppressed, stood in constant opposition to one another, carried on an uninterrupted, now hidden, now open fight, a fight that each time ended, in a revolutionary reconstruction of society at large, or in common ruin of contending classes. (p. 79)

In *If... Tragedy of the Ruled*, Rotimi openly calls for the unification of the oppressed. Though, the oppressor in the play has the upper hand in the “ruin” that ultimately creeps into the compound, it is crystal clear that Rotimi’s sentiments, like all Marxists, lie deeply with the oppressed. The death of the young Onyema does not depict futility in the struggle for integration, for unity, but a clear manifestation and exposition of the stupidity of those who abuse their position of power in Nigeria and elsewhere in the human race.

In the same vein above, Ukala’s treatment of the fragmentation of the aggregate units that build the Nigerian state by the handiwork of those that be in order to continue their stranglehold on the socio-

political and economic largesse of the nation, is a clear warning that all will never remain the same all the time. Ukala invariably posits that a time will come when the oppressed will rise and that the outcome, as Marx and Engels above posit, will either culminate “in a revolutionary reconstruction of society at large, or in common ruin of contending classes” (p. 79). *The Placenta of Death* ends in the latter, with both the elite, royalty, rich, poor, all drowning in the web of disintegration they create. For just as the political class continue to invent means of entrenching their dominance even if it destroys the unity of the country, the oppressed, as the African adage says, when the goat is pushed to the wall, it develops the teeth to bite, will come up with a means of survival, of self preservation, even if such means is taken to the extreme as the case in *The Placenta of Death*. In Nigeria, youth have taken to such extremes, kidnapping, blowing oil pipelines (as in *The Niger Delta*), have taken to the streets to demand for secession (as in the Eastern part of Nigeria) and others have taken to religious fundamentalism (as in the northern part of the country). Ukala, in *The Placenta of Death* warns that when the gulf between the rich and the poor, the rulers and the ruled, between the various fragments of society is too wide, extremism is inevitable. This is why Asagba (2008, p.90) notes it that in “Ukala’s vision of a new society built on democratic principles, values and justice, the process of

retributive justice is immediate, not a futuristic phenomenon’. That Omon, from the kindred of the poor, cooks her own placenta to poison the Oba and his guests, is out of frustration; frustration of stigmatization, of people stealing her pride, her joy of human dignity. Her father, Iziegbe, exonerates her of wrong doing:

IZIEGBE: Eat, my daughter, eat. You’ve not done the abominable. It’s Owodo who has done it. You bore him a prince, just as Ibo. We were right to expect his gift, the type he sent to Ibo. But the rich know only how to look after themselves. Don’t worry. Our time will come. My grandson will rule Owodoland. He is the weapon by which we will make the rich to eat sand (p. 44).

Similarly Ibo, who is considered a slave also, has her own plan to rid herself and her lineage of servitude, of the stigma of slavery:

IBO: (*Addressing her baby*) the whole of his courtyard is yours. From here, you’ll sneeze and the whole of Owodoland will quiver. Here you’ll sit to make the captor the captive, the enslaver the slave. King-the-sky, come. Come sit on your throne...(p. 34).

Thus, to free herself and her lineage of the pangs and stigma of slavery, Ibo goes extreme, after she

married the king. She makes herself a tyrant to the so-called freeborn, takes the portion meant for the freeborn-wife of the king and even goes diabolical. This is what happens when there is fragmentation, disunity and distrust in a land.

The need for National Integration

According to Monyeh 2007 cited in Osammor (2012, p.76),

There is no doubt that the people of Nigeria are concerned about the issue of National Development. But many factors seem to be militating against the progress of the nation, one of which is the issue of unity among the divergent people of Nigeria. It is therefore pertinent that for progress, unity in diversity must be the watchword.

The need for national integration therefore cannot be overemphasized. It makes the citizens develop and imbibe the spirit of responsiveness to issues of national (not just ethnic) interest. By extension it engenders patriotism and loyalty to national course. National integration also encourages peaceful co-existence of the many quasi-ethnic nationalities in the country. Such co-existence is vital for peace, which is a vital index of national development. It also rekindles the spirit of patriotism and loyalty to the national project. National integration also rejuvenates our collective spirit of communism, which tends more to humanism than the cut-throat capitalism that

makes people see other people as potential “customer” and not as brother.

Conclusion and Way Forward

That our dear country, Nigeria is in dire need of national integration is not a question. The problem is how do we achieve it in the face of a corrupt, sectional and greedy leadership? The plays reviewed in this paper submit it all: we, as a people must imbibe the spirit of good followership, we must not always succumb to corrupt tendencies, we must resist evil policies, we must open our eyes widely to discern evil from good. In this case, we must ask questions and demand accountability from our leaders. Also, we must be able to elect upright leaders on the platform of free and fair elections. We must never sell our votes for a pinch of salt. It is also imperative that we must come to grasp with the fact that though we live as a nation, we are diverse culturally and every quasi culture must learn to respect the other’s cultures. This is very vital for a unified Nigeria. Value orientation is thus, key to national integration. It is only when, as citizens, we do all these, that we become good leaders and good followers.

References

- Asagba, A. O. "Sam Ukala and the new Nigerian theatre. *Sam Ukala: His Works at Sixty*. Ed. Austin O. Asagba. Ibadan: Kraft Books. 2008. 81-92.
- Campbell, R. Martin, C. R. & Fabos, B. (2009). *Media and culture*. Bedford: New York
- Danjuma, T.Y. (2018). "Armed Forces Collude With Those Behind Killings" <https://www.channelstv.com/2018/03/24/armed-forces-collude-with-those-behind-killings-says-t-y-danjuma/>
- Ekoko (2012:1). "Security is about people". *Abraka humanities review*. Special Edition. 1-18
- Marx, K. & Engels, F. (1988). *The Communist Manifesto*. Middlesex: Penguin Books.
- Ojo, B. (2013) "How to achieve national integration". <http://thenationonlineng.net/how-to-achieve-national-integration-by-ojo/>. Retrieved on 15th May, 2018.
- Okpe, O. O. (2003). "The Sovereign national conference: an historical appraisal of contending issues and their implications for the corporeality of the Nigerian nation". *The Sovereign national conference*. Ed. Okpe, O. O. Jnr. Makurdi: Aboki Publishers. 1-34.
- Oputa, C. (2005). "Don't expect anything new from confab". Saturday Sun. May 28.
- Osammor, (2012:76) "Achieving unity as precursor to national security through the dance art: the Nigeriana paradigm". *WAJASS*. Vol. 3 (1) 75-79.
- Punch (2018) "Blame Buhari, Osinbajo, NSA, IG for Benue killings, Ortom tells Senate" <http://punchng.com/blame-buhari-osinbajo-nsa-ig-for-benue-killings-ortom-tells-senate/> Punch Jan. 14, 2018. Retrieved on 15th May, 2018.
- Rotimi, O. (1983). *If... Tragedy of the Ruled*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books (Nig) ltd.
- Ukala, S. (2007). *The placenta of death in Two plays : The placenta of death and the last heroes*. Ibadan: Kraftgriots
- Ukala, S. (2012). "The humanities and the rehumanization of Africans for security". *Abraka humanities review*. Special Edition. 19-38
- Umukoro, M. O. (2010). *Creative drama and theatre in education: a resource handbook*. Ughelli: Eregha press